

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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ANNOTATION

Today, in the personnel training system, a lot of work is being done to bring the development of communicative knowledge and skills to a new level and to accelerate educational reforms in this regard.

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Today, in the personnel training system, a lot of work is being done to bring the development of communicative knowledge and skills to a new level and to accelerate educational reforms in this regard. Reforms carried out in all areas of our society are also affecting the continuing education system. New goals and tasks are being set for general education schools. At the center of the purpose and essence of all changes are issues such as the developing personality of the student - his goal and self-awareness, his development as a person, and the acquisition of communication skills. It is not for nothing that educating the young generation in Uzbekistan on the basis of communicative competence has become an issue at the level of state policy. Because communicativeness develops in a society where the freedom of young people is ensured, and freedom of thought is the guarantee of a strong society. After all, "our only goal is to transform pre-school education and school education, higher and secondary special education system, and scientific and cultural institutions into the four integral nations of the Third Renaissance, and our kindergarten teachers, school teachers, professors, and scientific and creative intellectuals into the four parts of the New Renaissance. is to turn it into a support pillar.

In this paragraph, the essence of the concept of communicative competence, its classification in dictionaries, its pedagogical significance, and the possibilities and current state of the educational system aimed at its formation are researched. Also, the organizational and legal foundations of the development of communicative worldview and thinking, the state of legal norms in practice are also covered. For this purpose, it is appropriate to clarify the content of the concept of competence first.

The term competence was first used in science in the 50s and 60s of the 20th century. The English concept of "competence" literally means a level of ability based on deep knowledge. The content means "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional competence, skill and talent." In general, in the definitions given to the concepts of "competence" and "competence", competence is the behavior and behavior required in a certain activity, and competence is interpreted as the degree of compliance with this requirement, that is, the final result of the demonstration of competence.

If the dictionary of terms from pedagogy is defined as "competence - knowledge in this or that field", then in the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan "competence - 1) the powers of a certain state body (local self-government body) or an official established by law, charter or other document, right and scope of duties; 2) defined as knowledge, experience in one or another field.

Based on research, 16 different meanings of the word competence are distinguished and they are as follows:

- the ability to solve production issues;
- ability to apply knowledge and skills in specific situations;
- compliance with the description of the professional standard;
- requirement imposed on the worker by the organization in order to form the quality activity of the subject;
- compatibility of the employee's behavioral norms with the organization;
- general sum of knowledge, skills and competences (SKM), ability, motivation, personality, communicative qualities and other concepts;
- quality work training and skills;
- responsibility and authority for job duties;
- BKM+ important professional qualities;
- various aspects of competence;
- deep understanding of professional experience in combination with important professional qualities and organizational context;
- personality, individuality;
- human factor in successful activity;
- criteria of effective production activity;
- creativity. Therefore, competence is a general combination of knowledge, skills, qualifications, causal factors, personal qualities, target situations.

According to research scientist I. Aliev, competence is understood as a certain acquired competence, that is, a fully formed set of certain qualities. This concept is described in dictionaries as "having knowledge that allows one to think about something", "to be aware, to be entitled". "The definition of competence is similar and replaces (complements) each other, while at the same time there is no single interpretation of the word competence, this concept is "a set of powers (rights and obligations) of some body or an official, determined by law, regulations of this body or another situations", "to have (possess) knowledge that allows one to think about something", "a set of questions (area) that someone is well informed about". Therefore, the meanings of competence have different meanings in different fields.

In fact, the concept of competence entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, communicates, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, and has a plan of movement in complex processes." Also, competences require constant enrichment of knowledge, learning of new information, understanding of important social requirements, ability to search for new information, process it and apply it in one's work. It is considered a real, formed personal quality based on knowledge, and it is an intellectual and personally determined social and professional formation of a person. Also, it includes a set of interrelated characteristics (knowledge, skills, methods of activity) identified

in connection with certain objects and processes and necessary for high-quality production activity in relation to them. Therefore, there is a separate, special requirement for students regarding their preparation in the educational process.

Communicative competence is a complex communicative skill and type of activity, which includes new social skills, communication norms and restrictions, knowledge, customs, etiquette, manners, educational orientations. According to research scientist N. Amirov, "the ability to communicate effectively, which we call today communicative competence, has always been of interest to many scientists." In the fields of sociology, social psychology, pedagogy, and other modern fields of knowledge, attention is focused on the theoretical study of interpersonal relations, communicative actions of the individual. Even now, there is a social need to increase the number of research works in the training of personnel, aimed at preparing them for effective communication from the time of school and increasing their knowledge about the culture of communication. For this, the importance of scientific recommendations that can be taken into account in the implementation of various educational reforms, in particular, in the transition of the education system to new state standards and in the training of future specialists, is growing. The main goal in the modern educational process is the organization of effective continuous education aimed at the development of students' personal abilities, scientific potential, knowledge, skills and qualifications. So, communicative competence is a general communicative characteristic of a person, which includes communication skills, knowledge, skills and social experience.

In the organization of pedagogical communication, it is not possible to proceed only from pedagogical goals and tasks, in fact, it is natural that they are the basis of the activity. The nature of communication in such a situation leads to the fact that the teacher always tries to communicate with him by expressing his opinion, that is, only "his" demand. In communication with children, it is important to communicate with children, not by expressing "one's own" demands, but by taking into account their interests and aspirations, so that the child is within the radius of pedagogical goals with his own interests and world.

The basis of communicative competence is formed by:

- communication organization — interpersonal communication skills;
- maintaining communication, contact, establishing feedback;
- analyzing the results of communication.

Communication skills include:

- to provide a socio-psychological forecast of the communicative situation in which communication is required;
- socio-psychological programming of the communication process, based on the uniqueness of the communicative situation;
- implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation.

A competent approach to education envisages teaching students to effectively use the competences formed in various situations in personal, professional and social life. Special attention is paid to the ability to use relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities when facing unexpected, uncertain, new, problematic situations. Therefore, in the process of teaching each subject, competences related to it are formed based on its content and characteristics. Professor A. Abdukadirov emphasizes the problem of formation and development of a competent approach in students, that the development of competence is a process that does

not stop during the whole life of a person. In the researches of our pedagogic scientists, the specific aspects of professional and pedagogic competence have been highlighted. For example, in his research, N.A. Muslimov cited communicative competence in the form of six qualities:

- 1) Motivational qualities (covers the needs, motives and goals for the chosen profession, which are formed and developed throughout a person's life);
- 2) Intellectual potential (on the basis of all official documents, the teacher strives to transfer information and data, to form knowledge, skills and qualifications);
- 3) Volitional qualities (striving for the goal, overcoming internal and external obstacles, physical and mental stress, self-control and initiative qualities);
- 4) Practical skills (psychological, pedagogical, methodical and technical-technological abilities, actions, skills of an individual in various spheres of activity and communication);
- 5) Emotional qualities (formation of the necessary skills to manage one's emotions (anger, anxiety, resentment, jealousy, sympathy, shame, pride, fear, joy, love, etc.) and understand one's emotional states and their causes);
- 6) Self-control (freedom in choosing goals and means of achieving them, conscientiousness, critical approach to one's activities, comprehensiveness and understanding of actions, comparing one's own behavior with that of others, confidence in the future, maintaining and managing one's physical and psychological condition at the required level receive). Various definitions of competence are given in the psychological and pedagogical literature: Communicative competence is a system necessary for internal resources, effective communicative construction and actions within a certain framework of interpersonal relationships. Therefore, it means the level of interpersonal experience formation, that is, communication skills and the potential to establish active relationships.

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